

Much ado about null things: A small replication crisis

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Summary

Replication is a big concern in contemporary science. At its core, replicable research can be repeated in different contexts, possibly using different tools, to obtain similar results. In geography, a recent replication study found a huge discrepancy: twice the number of significant "clusters" in local Moran's I statistics were detected in one software package relative to other packages. We show that this replication failure is a conceptual, not technical, issue: different "null hypotheses" used in local tests are not directly comparable. We show the conceptual issue, demonstrate it empirically, and then reflect on its implications for calls for "weak" replication in spatial science.

KEYWORDS: replication, statistical testing, reproducibility, statistical testing, local indicators of spatial association

1. Introduction

Replication is critical in contemporary science. At its core, replicable research can be repeated in different contexts, possibly using different tools, to obtain similar results. Over the last decade, software implementations have grown rapidly throughout the research community (Bivand, Pebesma, and Gomez-Rubio (2013); Rey et al. (2021)) alongside increasing adoption of "local statistics" throughout science. This proliferation raises the stakes for replication in geography, since a study can be conducted and repeated in many analytical environments. Ideally, our interpretations of an analysis ought to be the same across environments.

Unfortunately, this is not the case. Bivand and Wong (2018) conducted a thorough review of different spatial statistical implementations in R, Python, and desktop geographic information systems. While many of the analyses replicated, Bivand and Wong (2018) found one, the Local Moran's I_i , had serious differences in local test results which yield different interpretations: an analyst using one computational environment might see very different structure, shape, and size of detected "clusters." Indeed, twice (or half) as many "significant" local statistics were found. Their main display is replicated in Figure 1. This failure to replicate important. Local statistics, and Local Moran's I_i particularly, are one of the most commonly-used analytical techniques in exploratory spatial data analysis. The logic of the statistic also finds its way into cutting-edge spatial machine learning (Klemmer & Neill 2021).

Where Goodchild and Li (2021) suggest that replication must be "weak" in the social and environmental sciences, they refer to (primarily) the idea that exact model specifications, structures, or estimates may not necessarily translate from context to context. We agree; sometimes processes will not have the same estimate values between different cases or software. However, there is *also* a case for "strong" replication in some epistemologically important areas of spatial analysis: if there is *anything* in spatial analysis that needs "strong" replication, it is that Local Moran's I statistics should find the same clusters and outliers across software environments. We must be internally rigorous about this. We need both

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Figure 1: clusters detected in Bivand and Wong (2018) using two different inferential methods from two different software packages (R’s *spdep* and Python’s *pysal*), reprised directly from Bivand and Wong (2018)’s Figure 9.

“strong” and “weak” replication: recalling King (1996), there are some situations where context should not count. This is one such situation.

2. An anatomy of replication failure

Bivand and Wong (2018) suggest the replication failure is due to a *permutation* estimator’s sensitivity to “spatial heteroskedasticity.” They evidence this tentative hypothesis with a visual association between the areas of maximal disagreement and an indicator of local variance. This makes sense, as there is a long and storied literature on the (non-)robustness of statistics to heteroskedasticity; sometimes, assuming that variance is constant (when it is not) will result in incorrect conclusions. In the context of recent discussions about “weak” replication in social sciences (Goodchild and Li, 2021), it makes sense that heterogeneity in variance affects our ability to compare results between different regions, times, estimators, software, or datasets.

Alternatively, we re-investigated the differences (Sauer et al. 2021) with a focus on the theoretical underpinnings of the two approaches. We show they imply different *null hypotheses*, which we argue drives the replication failure. Different nulls are expected to give different conclusions. For example, a *t*-test can find a significant difference in a one-tailed setup but fail to find this under a two-tailed setup. The nulls in these cases are different: *knowing* that a test ought to be applied in a specific direction lets you “see” more in that direction. Unfortunately, this is much more subtle for inference on local Moran’s I_i .

2.1 The classic statistical test for Local Moran’s I

Most of the local testing frameworks derive from the mathematics of Cliff and Ord (1981), which operates under a “total randomization” null. It characterizes the probability of obtaining the local statistic under random shuffles of the observed map. This provides an “analytical” mathematical expression for the expected value and variance of local Moran’s I_i statistics:

$$\mathbf{E}[I_i] = \frac{-\sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij}}{n-1} \quad (1)$$

$$\mathbf{Var}[I_i] = w_{i(2)}(n-b_2)/(n-1) + 2w_{i(kh)}(2b_2-n)/[(n-1)(n-2)] - \frac{w_i^2}{(n-1)^2} \quad (2)$$

	"Total" Randomization Null <i>shuffle all values, so each value is equally likely at any site</i>	"Conditional" Randomization Null <i>for each site, the site's value is fixed and remaining sites are shuffled</i>
Analytical estimator <i>closed-form mathematical expressions for test statistics</i>	Originally in Anselin (1995). Implemented in pysal and spdep . Used in Bivand & Wong (2018). Denoted here as $E[I_i]$ and $Var[I_i]$	Originally in Sokal (1998). Not implemented in pysal and spdep or considered by Bivand & Wong (2018). Denoted here as $E_c[I_i]$ and $Var_c[I_i]$
Permutation estimator <i>test statistics computed from set of simulated maps</i>	Not considered or implemented.	Originally in Anselin (1995). Implemented in pysal . Used in Bivand and Wong (2018). Denoted here as $E_p[I_i]$ and $Var_p[I_i]$

Figure 2 (from Sauer et al. 2021), the three inferential methods for Local Moran's I .

Then, assuming that statistics are approximately normal, significance can be assessed using a “z-score”:

$$Z(I_i) = \frac{I_i - \mathbf{E}[I_i]}{\sqrt{\mathbf{Var}[I_i]}} \quad (3)$$

2.2 Permutation methods to assess the conditional randomization null

However, the so-called “permutation estimator” stated (and preferred) by Anselin (1995) works differently: the site value is held fixed, the *rest of the map* is shuffled, and a “null” statistic computed. Because this computational procedure synthesizes a reference distribution of “null” statistics directly, inference is typically *not* done analytically. That is, it does not use a mathematical expression for the test statistic like done in the classical approach from Section 2.1. Instead, the observed statistic is compared against the quantiles of this reference distribution: if the observed statistic is in the tail, it is unlikely to have arisen under this null. Fortunately, this does not make assumptions about the normality of I_i under the null, as is done by all the other tests considered here.

To make direct comparisons, however, Bivand and Wong (2018) synthesize z-scores for the local Moran's I_i statistics. These are obtained from the permutation estimator using the same normality assumption from Equation (3). The mean and variance of the reference distribution stand in for the expectation and variance of local I_i . The strategy is the bottom right of Figure 2.

2.3 An alternative analytical method to assess the conditional randomization null

In fact, the “permutation” estimator implies a different null hypothesis for local Moran's I_i , since the null must *condition* (i.e. hold constant) the value at each site, thus the “conditional” randomization null. We found Sokal et al. (1998) provide an analytical expression for the moments of the local I_i statistic under this null. That is, Sokal et al (1998) define an *analytical estimator* of $Z(I_i)$ under the “conditional” randomization null; this is the top right part of the table in Figure 2:

$$\mathbf{E}_c[I_i] = -z_i^2 \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n w_{ij}}{n-1} \quad (4)$$

$$\mathbf{Var}_c[I_i] = \left[\frac{z_i}{m_2} \right]^2 \left[\frac{n}{n-2} \right] \left[w_{i(2)} - \frac{w_i^2}{n-1} \right] \left[m_2 - \frac{z_i^2}{n-1} \right] \quad (5)$$

This differs from the form of the classical test for local Moran's I_i expressed in Equations (1) and (2). The value of the site variate z_i is directly involved in both the expected value and variance: it is “held constant” while the rest of the map is shuffled. In contrast, the classic expected value (Eq. 1) is constant when the weights are row-standardized (as is overwhelmingly done in practice) and the variance depends on the number of connections each site has, but not the data at each site. Constructing a z-score with this

Figure 3 Distributions of the three estimator & null hypothesis pairings from Figure 2 for Bivand and Wong (2018)’s data.

mean and variance yields a third statistic that can be used to conduct inference.

3. Results

With this “third” analytical estimator of the conditional randomization hypothesis, we confirm that there is near-exact correspondence between the analytical and permutation estimator under a conditional randomization null. This holds in heteroskedastic experiments and applied settings. This suggests that Bivand and Wong (2018)’s differences are driven by this subtle change in null hypothesis, rather any estimator’s lack of robustness. Figure 3 shows the extreme correspondence in Bivand and Wong (2018)’s empirical example, and Sauer et al. (2021) discusses these findings in detail.

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